

IMPROVEMENT OF CIVIL SERVANTS PERFORMANCE AT THE MINISTRY OF RELIGION OFFICE OF JEMBER REGENCY

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Abstract

Performance is the result of work that can be raised by someone or a group of people in an organization, in accordance with their respective powers and responsibilities. It is an effort to achieve the goal of the organization legally while do not violate the law and in accordance with morals and ethics. The purpose of the research is to know about the effect of the application of fingerprint, food allowance and performance allowance to the civil servants. The researcher used multiple linier regression analysis, f test and t test as data analysis. Sample that is used by the researcher is saturated sampling with 51 respondents. The result of the research shows that those three things are simultaneously have a significant effect to the civil servants. A very dominant variable in this research is the application of fingerprint.

Keywords: application of fingerprint, civil servants performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The success of an organization cannot be separated from increasing human resources. Superior and quality human resources must always be managed and emphasized by the organization to achieve the expected performance. Therefore, improving the quality of human resources is needed so that employees have attitudes and behaviors that are able to provide services and guidance and also inner well-being to the community. (Susilaningsih, 2008: 3).

Performance is the basis for achieving the goals of an organization especially at the Ministry of Religion office of Jember regency. The success in improving the performance of Civil Servants (PNS) is very dependent on the quality of the human resources involved in working while in the institution. Furthermore, the role of human resources on the performance of government institutions is very important, decisions on human resources must be able to improve efficiency and even be able to provide improved performance results of Civil Servants (PNS) at the

Ministry of Religion office of Jember regency and also have an impact on improving service satisfaction. (Logahan, 2009: 3).

The application of fingerprints, food allowance and performance allowance for Civil Servants (PNS) at the Ministry of Religion office of Jember Regency is expected to improve their performance. In addition, it is necessary to support a good work environment in the form of a work environment that can support smoothness, safety, safety, cleanliness, and comfort in work and the availability of adequate facilities so that employees feel safe, calm and happy in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. (Suprayitno, 2007: 24).

Several previous studies (Widiastuti; 2016, Setiawan; 2015, Ahmad; 2016, Novianto; 2012) whose results state the variable application of fingerprint affects employee performance. A research conducted by Ulfa et al (2014) states that giving food allowance affects employee performance. It is also strengthened by several researchs (Mulyadi; 2012, Sirajuddin Saleh, Muhammad Darwis; 2015), with the results state that performance allowance variables affect employee performance.

From this background, the purpose of this study was to examine and analyze the effect of the application of fingerprints, food allowance and performance allowance on the performance of Civil Servants (PNS) at the Ministry of Religion office of Jember regency.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

Research Object

The Ministry of Religion office of Jember regency is located on Jl. KH. Wahid Hasyim No.1, Kepatihan village, Kaliwates subdistrict, Jember regency, East Java Province is a government institution that carries out part of the government's duties in the religious field, such as the Hajj, marriage, religious education, religious harmony and inter-religious harmony.

Population dan Sample

The population in this study is Civil Servants (PNS) in the office by taking samples using saturated sampling method of 51 people.

Research Variable and Measurement

This study consists of two (2) kinds of variables, namely independent variables or variables that do not depend on other variables and dependent variables or variables that depend on other variables.

Independent variable which is mentioned is the application of fingerprint, food allowance and performance allowance. While the dependent variable mentioned is employee performance. The application of fingerprint is a software that supports for the purposes of presence which includes income, data entry and time lapses, and processing the data into a report that will be used for policy taking by the leader, because filling in manual attendance (only in the form of a presence list book) will make an obstacle for agencies to monitor employee discipline in terms of the time of arrival and home hours every day. Some measurement indicators from the application of fingerprint, first: employees do not need to bother carrying cards, employees do not need to press passwords or pins that are troublesome just enough to put our fingers right above the fingerprint sensor (aspect of convenience), second: fingerprint users cannot leave attendance as performed using manual signature (aspect of security), third: fingerprint

usage is faster than *amano*, barcode, or manual signature (time effectiveness), fourth: fingerprint prescription is much more efficient when compared to voice or retina identification or with *amano* that make the office have to spend the expense of buying paper, ink and maintenance service monthly.

Food allowance is money given to Civil Servants (PNS) based on tariffs and daily calculation for food needed by Civil Servants (PNS). Food allowance is not given to Civil Servants (PNS) in the following conditions: they are absent from work, are on official travel, are on leave, are undergoing study assignments and / or other causes that make them do not deserve of being given food allowance. The provision of food allowance is based on the attendance list of the work of the Civil Servants (PNS), paid once in a month, the earliest at the beginning of the following month, for example the December food allowance is paid in the month concerned with the adjusted attendance in the month concerned.

Performance allowance is a form of direct compensation paid to employees because their performance exceeds the prescribed standard. This system is another form of direct wages outside steam and salary which is a fixed compensation called a compensation system based on performance (pay for performance plan). Indicators and measurements of performance allowance are motivating employees to work so that employees are more eager to work in order to meet their needs. It can also guarantee the principle of justice that is giving employees a fair feeling to increase their loyalty. The allowance can be given in the form of goods or money to improve employee performance.

Performance measurement is a formal business carried out systematically by the management in evaluating the results that have been achieved by utilizing the resources owned by the company efficiently and effectively in a period to achieve the goals or mission set by the company. Indicators of performance measurement of Civil Servants (PNS) compare between the realization of work and the target and seen from the elements of behavior consisting of aspects of service orientation, integrity, commitment, discipline, cooperation, and leadership.

Analysis Tool

Data collection methods in this study were using interview, observation and questionnaire methods. Data analysis methods used in this study were first: Data Validity Test consisting of 1) Validity Test, 2) Reliability Test, second: Classic Assumption Test consisting of 1) Normality Test, 2) Multicollinearity Test, 3) Heteroskedastistas Test, third: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis, fourth: Hypothesis Test consisting of 1) Simultaneous Testing (Test F), 2) Partial Testing (t test).

3. ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH RESULTS

Analysis of the data used in this study is divided into 2 parts, the first is according to the statistical description with the questionnaire respondents totaling 51 people with the total return of the questionnaire is 100%. The second is according to the description of the respondents, namely a) The sex of the many respondents is male gender at 72.5%, while the few respondents are female gender at 27.5%; b) The last education of the most respondents is S1 (stratum 1) of 52.9%, while the rest of respondent have Diploma as their last education, which is 3.9%; and c) The highest age of respondents are those with ages 40-49 years, amounting to 45.1%, while the lowest respondents are those with 30-39 years of age, which is 23.5%.

By using multiple linear regression analysis, the value of the constant value (a) is positive at 1,860 which can be interpreted if the performance of the Civil Servants (PNS) at the Ministry of Religion office of Jember regency

will increase if the variables of application of fingerprint, food allowance and performance allowance are fulfilled properly. The magnitude of the variable regression coefficient of the application of fingerprint is positive at 0.658 meaning that the higher / disciplined Civil Servants (PNS) at the Ministry of Religion office of Jember regency do fingerprint when the hours of entry and hours go home, the better performance is increasing. The magnitude of the regression coefficient variable of food allowance is positive at 0.068 which means that the greater the food allowance received by the Civil Servants (PNS) at the Ministry of Religion office of Jember Regency, the better performance is increasing. The magnitude of the regression coefficient of performance allowance is negative at 0.338, meaning that the higher the performance allowance received by the Civil Servants (PNS) at the Ministry of Religion office of Jember regency, the better performance will increase.

Based on the results of processing with the SPSS program version 16, it was obtained f test of 19.068 with sig 0.000. Sig value obtained value <0.05 and f count $> f$ table with f table is $19.068 > 2.80$, thus proving the variable of application of fingerprint, food allowance and performance allowance has a significant effect simultaneously or together on the performance of Civil Servants (PNS) at the Ministry of Religion office of Jember regency.

By using the t test, it is found that a) the variable implementation of fingerprint results obtained t count of $3.125 > t$ table of 2.01174 means that partially the application of fingerprint variables significantly influence the performance of Civil Servants (PNS) at the Ministry of Religion office of Jember regency; b) variable of food allowance obtained results of t count of 0.378 $< t$ table of 2.01174, which means that partially the variable of food allowance has no significant effect on the performance of Civil Servants (PNS) at the Ministry of Religion office of Jember regency; c) performance allowance variables obtained results of t count of 1.563 $< t$ table of 2.01174, which means that partially the performance allowance variable has no significant effect on the performance of Civil Servants at the Ministry of Religion office of Jember regency.

4. INTERPRETATION

From the analysis results, it can be explained that simultaneously X1, X2, X3 affect employee performance. This supports the research of Widiyastuti (2016), Mulyadi (2012), Sirajuddin Saleh, Muhammad Darwis (2015) which state the variables of fingerprint, food allowance and performance allowance affects employees performance.

While partially only fingerprint variables that affect employee performance. The results of this study are in accordance with the results of research by Widiyastuti (2016), Setiawan (2015), Ahmad (2006) which state the application of fingerprint affects employee performance.

The results of this study reject the results of the research by Ulfah et al (2014), Sirajuddin Saleh, Muhammad Darwis (2015), Mulyadi (2012) which state the variable of food allowance and performance allowance influences employees performance. It happens due to food allowance cutting which is relatively small that is equal to 3%, and because the provision of performance allowance based on performance achievement reports still uses manuals and is made at the end of the month.

From the results of this research, it can be explained that fingerprint is a dominant variable affecting employee performance because presence using fingerprint is very effective in reducing cheating on manual attendance, deprogrammed fingerprints in such a way that it is difficult to be manipulated by employees who arrive late or leave early or employees who leave it absent by other employees.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the data analysis, it was found that the variable implementation of fingerprint, food allowance and performance allowance simultaneously or together has a significant effect on performance. While partially it was found that the variable of implementation of fingerprint has a significant effect on employee performance, variable of food allowance has an effect but not significant on employees performance and performance allowance variables have an effect but not significant on the performance of civil servants (PNS) are predominantly influenced by the variable application of fingerprint.

6. IMPLICATION

The application of fingerprint, food allowance and performance allowance are factors that affect the performance of Civil Servants (PNS) at the Ministry of Religion office of Jember Regency, and the application of fingerprint is the dominant factor affecting the performance of Civil Servants at the Ministry of Religion office of Jember regency. Furthermore, it still needs a space for innovation, creativity and motivation of leaders so that other factors can further improve the performance of Civil Servants (PNS) at the Ministry of Religion office of Jember regency.

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